

Identity Crisis of Second Derivatives

A Note on Stock-Flow Identification

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September 3, 2025

Abstract

System dynamics textbooks do not provide clear guidelines for distinguishing stocks from flows. Some resources even suggest that a variable can be formulated as stock or flow depending on the topic at hand. A well-known example is velocity, which, according to some, can be modeled as flow if the question concerns distance or as stock if the question centers around the velocity itself. This paper argues that for quality control, modeling standardization, and educational purposes, we need a clearer guideline for stock-flows identification. To this end, stock and flow definitions and identification tests are reviewed and revised. A preliminary algorithm is developed to formalize the identification process. Potential future research and practice are also discussed.

1 Introduction

Distinguishing stocks (levels) from flows (rates) is a challenging phase of model formulation (Randers, 1980). It is well documented that many struggle to make such a distinction (Stermann, 2010). The challenge is not so apparent when dealing with tangible variables. It is relatively easy to conceptualize the volume of water behind a reservoir as a stock (Ford, 2010). We can tell with relative ease that population is also a stock variable. The challenge appears in problems that involve intangibles. It is not obvious if *velocity* is a flow or a stock. At first glance, velocity is a *flow*: it changes the stock of distance in a particular direction. This presumes that we already have identified the type of the other variable, *distance*. Now, what if we add acceleration to the mix? *Acceleration* is defined as the rate of change of velocity. Therefore, it must be a flow to the *stock* of velocity. Some teaching materials, e.g., Hannon and Ruth (2001, p. 364), Glass-Husain (1991, p. 33), and Bossel (2007a, p. 115), have formulated velocity both as stock and

flow. This confusion is not limited to abstract phenomena. Relatively tangible concepts such as supply and demand of goods and services (defined by economists as flows) are also formulated as stocks or flows depending on the question (Mass, 1980, p. 95). Can a variable have a dual nature in the real world, i.e., be flow and stock simultaneously? If yes, will there be any benefit or harm in limiting this nature to be singular for modeling purposes? Will there be any benefit or harm in assuming a dual nature for model variables? This paper comments on these conceptualization dilemmas.

Stock-flow identification is a critical step in formulating a system dynamics model (Randers, 1980). It is especially vital for successful policy design and analysis. Confusing stocks with flows can cause myopia in decision-making and possibly unintended consequences (Sterman, 2000, p. 192). After defining the main feedback loops of a model (model boundary) one needs to determine the stocks and flows of the system (Forrester, 1968). The two variable types are necessary and sufficient for a system dynamics model (Forrester, 1971). Auxiliaries and constants are not primary variable types. Auxiliaries are used to divide the equation of a flow into manageable pieces. Constants are stocks that do not change over the simulation time. Thus, variable identification has two steps (Figure 1): 1) identify stocks and flows, and 2) identify auxiliaries and constants. Once a variable is identified as a stock (and not a flow), we should decide whether to model it as a stock, constant, or auxiliary depending on its time constant (Richardson, 2022). Similarly, flows could be modeled as flow or auxiliaries depending on whether their corresponding stocks are modeled as stock or not. These model formulation choices (step 2) are important but well out of the scope of this paper. Instead, the focus is on step 1, i.e., distinguishing stocks from flows, henceforth referred to as *stock-flow identification*.

Confusions and inconsistencies in distinguishing stocks from flows point to a potentially systematic issue probably caused by lack of sufficient instructions in our educational materials for identifying variable types. Some textbooks do not provide any instructions for stock-flow identification, e.g., Roberts et al. (1994); Deaton and Winebrake (1999); Hannon and Ruth (2001). In others, the instructions are ambiguous. The *snapshot test* (explained later in the paper) is suggested only as a “rule-of-thumb” (Forrester, 1971, sec. 4.3) to check whether a variable is a stock or flow. Some textbooks imply that this is not the ultimate measure and that a variable could be stock or flow, depending on the model’s purpose. Richardson and Pugh III (1981, p. 177) write: “. . . averaging involves an accumulation over time, implying that average sales is *more like* [emphasis added] a level than a rate.” Further, some instructions in the literature appear to contradict each other.

Figure 1: The stock-flow identification process as a part of model conceptualization

Sterman (2000, p. 198) suggests that the units of measure could be used for stock-flow identification. In contrast, Forrester (1971, sec. 4.3) believed that units “do not indicate whether the variable is a level or a rate.” Richardson and Pugh III (1981, p. 177) echoed this opinion by writing, “[u]nits are no help in selecting level variables.” Nevertheless, we will see later that this last statement is accurate and could be useful for stock-flow identification.

Clear guidelines for model conceptualization and formulation benefit the field by

- improving modeling education and training,
- facilitating quality control of models, and
- enhancing standardization of modeling processes.

This paper aims to open a discussion among system dynamics educators and scholars regarding the stock-flow identification process and effective methods of teaching it. Enhanced teaching methods will help our students to improve their model formulation skills. These methods could also help us develop robust criteria for model diagnostics and documentation tools such as the System Dynamics Model Documentation and Assessment Tool (SDM-Doc) (MartinezMoyano, 2012), which was designed to spot problematic model misspecifications. Improved standardization is another benefit important for system dynamics software development and the potential use of artificial intelligence (AI) in modeling processes.

Organized as follows, this paper revisits model formulation in system dynamics by focusing on the gaps in stock-flow identification methods and suggests strategies to bridge the gaps. First, it provides a background of the

stock-flow identification methods. Then, it comments on potential issues of the current methods, and identifies the gaps. After that, it argues against the ambiguity of stock-flow identification guidelines and for more robust criteria. Following that, it suggests an enhanced method to define and identify stocks and flows. The paper then concludes with a summary and directions for future research.

2 Stocks and Flows

Besides the explicit notion of feedback loops, introducing stock-flow taxonomy to represent accumulation as the main driver of all changes in the world is probably the most prominent, innovative feature of system dynamics. As Forrester (1971, sec. 4.3) puts it: “Interconnecting feedback loops form any system. But at a lower hierarchy, each feedback loop contains a substructure. There are two fundamental types of variable elements within each loop – the levels, and the rates. Both are necessary. The two are sufficient.” This simple taxonomy is elegant, universal, and capable of characterizing systems in various domains, including manufacturing, biology, psychology, ecology, economics, public policy, etc.

Despite its elegance, dividing the real-world variables into two groups of stocks and flows is not trivial. Although system dynamicists believe that viewing the world as accumulation is more useful and easier to grasp than differentiation (Forrester, 1968), conceptualizing a problem in terms of stocks and flows or comprehending an accumulation process is hard (Sternman, 2010). This conceptualization difficulty contrasts with the original promise of the field, which was to help people understand a system’s dynamics through the stock-flow (accumulation) lens.

To conceptualize a problem in terms of stocks and flows, we must clearly define these variable types. The definition of flows in system dynamics textbooks usually relies on that of stocks. Most sources do not go into detailed technicalities and merely describe flows as the stocks’ rates of change.

Forrester (1971, sec. 4.4) provides a relatively detailed definition for flows. He defines them as “decisions” or “actions” generated by “policy statements.” From this perspective, a policy statement is equivalent to a flow equation as it drives a stream of decisions or actions. Stocks then accumulate the effect of the decisions or actions. In mathematical terms, flow is a derivative of stock, or stock is an integration of flow. As the definition of flow is derived from that of stock, the rest of this section provides a more detailed description of stocks.

Stocks, also known as levels, reservoirs, or states, are defined using many different accounts and styles, e.g., Forrester (1971, sec. 4.3), Richardson and Pugh III (1981, 176), Bossel (1994, p. 101), and Ford (2010, p. 32), revealing the challenging nature of describing and identifying a stock. Sterman (2000, p. 192) compiles the majority of the key elements offered by other sources in one account:

Stocks are accumulations. They characterize the state of the system and generate the information upon which decisions and actions are based. Stocks give systems inertia and provide them with memory. Stocks create delays by accumulating the difference between the inflow to a process and its outflow. By decoupling rates of flow, stocks are the source of disequilibrium dynamics in systems.

Although prudently worded, this definition is still too long with five statements, yet incomplete. As we will see later, there exists at least one case that fits this definition (so to be identified as a stock) but fails to pass the snapshot test (so not to be identified as a stock).

To perform a snapshot test, “imagine that all activity in a system is brought to rest. Only the level variables would remain and be observable. In a stationary system, all action would be frozen but all levels would continue to exist. A tree would stop growing, but the level of its accumulated height would be visible. In a factory, activity would have stopped, but the levels representing a number of employees, work in progress, capital equipment, and bank balance would be measurable. The more intangible levels would likewise remain – employee morale, company reputation, and quality of the product. Current instantaneous sales rate would have disappeared, but the knowledge of average sales rate for the past year would remain as a system-level” (Forrester, 1971, sec. 4.3).

This and other snapshot test instructions, e.g., Richardson and Pugh III (1981, pp. 176-7), Sterman (2000, p. 199), Bossel (2007c, p. 8), and Pruyt (2013, p. 39), are ambiguous for some cases and may not lead to a clear-cut conclusion regarding a variable type. It is especially true for intangible variables. For example, how can we know that “employee morale” remains if time is paused? If we stop time and take a photograph of the system, will we be able to observe morale? Can we measure it? We will discuss these issues later.

3 Identity Crisis of Velocity

Velocity is an example of the difficulty in stock-flow identification. As mentioned earlier, some sources have presented velocity as both flow and stock, even in the same model. So, the question is whether velocity is flow, stock, or both.

By definition, instantaneous velocity (velocity for short) is a flow. Plainly stated, velocity is the *rate of change* in an object's position relative to a specific location (consult with a physics textbook, e.g., Halliday et al. (2013) for technical details). According to this definition, velocity is the net flow to the stock of distance from a reference point. Velocity cannot be an accumulation (stock) because it is a *derivative* (of the stock of distance) and cannot exist in a stationary world. To measure velocity, we will need a speedometer that includes an integrator. "Every instrument that measures, that purports to measure, velocity lags the real world. It has some sort of integration process in it because it has to make a comparison between the present and the past in order to arrive at a velocity" (Forrester, 1999). It can be generalized to the broader concept of flows (Forrester, 1971, sec. 4.3):

No rate of flow can be measured instantaneously. All instruments that purport to measure rates actually require time for their functioning. They measure, not the instantaneous rate, but rather the average rate over some time interval. Likewise, we see that time is required to observe action in social systems and that measured rates are actually observed averages.

Nonetheless, one may argue that velocity should be modeled as a stock because we can also define it as an accumulation of acceleration. In this case, acceleration would be a net flow to the stock of velocity. Forrester has once formulated velocity as a stock Forrester (2009, p. 14). In some cases, as mentioned previously, velocity is considered a stock and a flow at the same time (Hannon and Ruth, 2001, p. 364; Glass-Husain, 1991, p. 33; Bossel, 2007a, p. 115). This confusion might be due to carelessness in distinguishing between *instantaneous* and *average* velocity. In contrast to instantaneous velocity, average velocity is an accumulation concept and should be conceptualized as a stock.

Velocity is not alone in this identity crisis. There are other variables that suffer from the same syndrome. *Production* is the most obvious alternative example. Production is an inflow to the stock of inventory. Similarly, a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a flow (Godley and Lavoie, 2012;

Wray, 2015). However, some textbooks have formulated GDP as a stock, e.g., Sterman (2000, p. 719) and Bossel (2007b, 103), probably because it can be considered as an accumulation of economic growth. Velocity and GDP have one thing in common: both are derivatives but have their own derivatives. In other words, the identity crisis emerges where well-known second or higher-order derivatives of a variable exist, at least in theory.

The identity crisis of flows is probably due to the vague definition of stock or our own lack of understanding of the concept being modeled. Velocity seems to possess all the stock characteristics as described by Sterman (2000, p. 192). It accumulates acceleration. It can characterize the state of the system if the state is of a moving object. It can give inertia, cause delays, and create disequilibrium in a system. At the same time, however, it fails the snapshot test. If time stops running, velocity ceases to exist. One may argue that we either need a better definition for stocks or a more decisive stock-flow identification test. Another valid argument is that our definitions are relative and subject to change depending on the problem at hand. A problem may require a variable to be defined as stock. Another may need it to be defined as flow. A more likely scenario is that we simply do not know enough about the problem at hand.

Can we have a relative definition of stocks and transform a stock into a flow? Consider *population*, for example. Can we model population as a flow? Does a situation (question) exist that requires such a conceptualization? How about an inventory of video game consoles? Can this inventory be modeled as a flow? Can we model a reservoir's water as a flow? The answer is *no*. None of these variables is a "rate of change" of any other variable in the real world. It was easy to answer these questions mainly because the definition of flow is relatively simple. We can run a variable type by the flow definition and rule out the possibility of it being a flow. If a variable is not a flow, then it should be stock.

What if we flip the question and ask if a flow can be stock? Can we model income as a stock? Can we model birth or death as stocks? Can we model precipitation as a stock? The answer depends on how we define stocks.

It is debatable whether our stock-flow definition and identification can impact the implication of a system dynamics model. Regardless of the true nature of stocks and flows, however, it might be more or less useful for modelers to consider stocks and flows as singular- or dual-nature. Next section comments on these issues.

4 Velocity “Should Not” Be a Stock

This paper argues that derivatives are *all* flows and *should not* be formulated as stocks if we agree that stocks “are the accumulations of the effect of past actions and continue to exist and can be observed even if there is no present activity” (Forrester, 1971, sec. 4.3). In a hypothetical situation where no activity exists, derivatives such as velocity and GDP will become meaningless as there will be no actions to drive velocity or production.

Regardless of our worldview about derivatives, we should refrain from formulating them as stocks for at least three practical reasons. First, it is still *more likely* that the true nature of a derivative is flow rather than stock. Mis-specifying a flow as a stock might lead to different and potentially misleading model results. Second, having a restrictive and clear definition and identification guideline for stocks and flows is key for effective system dynamics education. Third, restrictive guidelines, in general, enable computer-aided quality control and standardization of system dynamics models.

4.1 Modeling consideration

If a model is misspecified, its outputs are likely to be unreliable. A material delay (a flow concept) that is formulated mistakenly as an information delay (a stock concept) generates wrong (unintended) results in certain conditions. Let us assume input to a first-order (material or information) delay is constant at 0 initially ($T = 0$), but then jumps to a higher level at some point in time ($T = 5$). Further assume that delay time of this example is constant initially ($T = 0$), but then suddenly drops at a later stage ($T = 10$). Whether the delay is formulated as material or information, the trajectory of its output could be different (Figure 2). It is easy to mathematically show why these two functions work differently. Intuitively, material delays conserve input but information delays do not. Changing delay time affects both inflow and outflow of the stock in an information delay system but it only affects the outflow in a material delay system. That is why, the material delay reacts to the change in delay time more aggressively. Why and how these two formulations are different is outside of the scope of this paper, though. What matters is that it is important to get the stock-flow conceptualization right. Otherwise, the simulation results might go wrong.

If a model is misspecified, its outputs are likely to be unreliable. An incorrectly formulated material delay (a flow concept) as an information delay (a stock concept) can lead to unintended and incorrect results under certain conditions.

Let's assume that the input to a first-order delay, whether material or information, is initially constant at 0, but then abruptly increases to a higher level at some point in time, say at $T = 5$. Additionally, suppose that the delay time for this example is constant initially, but then suddenly decreases at a later stage, say at $T = 10$. Conceptualizing this delay example as material or information will define the trajectory of its output (see Figure 2). Mathematically, it can be easily demonstrated why these two functions behave differently. Intuitively, material delays conserve input, while information delays do not. The alteration of delay time affects both the inflow and outflow of the stock in an information delay system, whereas it only affects the outflow in a material delay system. Consequently, the material delay responds more aggressively to the delay time change.

Figure 2: Output of first-order material and information delays with a step function as input

The reasons behind and the specifics of these two formulations' differences are beyond the scope of this paper. What is crucial, however, is the importance of accurately distinguishing stocks from flows. Failing to do so may lead to incorrect simulation results.

Consider another example. Sterman (2000, p. 719) provides a macroeconomic accounting model where GDP is formulated as a stock. In macroeconomics, however, GDP is aggregate supply (AS), an inflow to the stock

of total inventory of goods and services in a national economy (Branson, 1989). No matter which definition (specification) is correct, assume GDP is a flow by nature. What if we misspecify it as stock, then?

Sterman (2000, p. 719) formulates GDP as an exponential smoothing function of aggregate demand (AD) with a one-year time delay (Figure 3). The delay is probably added to enable the integration process and ensure unit consistency. However, in the original macroeconomic accounting model, there is no delay between AD and GDP. These variables are identical measures of economic performance, and both share the same equation, i.e., $GDP = AD = C + I + G$, where C is the consumption of goods and services, I is investment expenditure, and G is the government (public) expenditure (Branson, 1989). This model represents a closed economy and excludes international trade. Note that GDP and AD might differ in the real world because AS is physically determined by the country's aggregate production capacity, which may not equalize AD. Nevertheless, macroeconomic accountants simplify the issue and assume these are equal.

Figure 3: A hypothetical model of macroeconomic accounting with GDP formulated as stock

We can reformulate Sterman's model with AD as an inflow and GDP as an outflow of the stock of inventory (Figure 4). This model will then be consistent with the macroeconomic accounting as there will be no delay between the two variables.

Using the initial setting presented in Sterman (2000, p. 719), it is trivial to show that the simulation results of these models (Figure 5) differ because in one GDP is an accumulation (stock). In the other, it is an instantaneous flow. The second model is more flexible as it can match the first model's output if GDP includes a first-order *material* delay of AD.

Here, we were not to decide which model was more realistic or useful

Figure 4: A hypothetical model of macroeconomic accounting with GDP formulated as flow

Figure 5: Comparison between simulation outputs of the same model with different stock-flow identification

but which was more consistent with macroeconomic and system dynamics theory. To make the model more realistic, one would follow Forrester’s operational approach to economic modeling (Saeed, 2014) rather than simply adding a one-year delay to GDP.

4.2 Educational consideration

A clear and more restrictive definition of stock variables helps us improve system dynamics education, thus avoiding the potential misspecification by future generations of modelers. Suppose textbooks emphasize stocks and flows as single-nature and provide a concise and clear definition and a robust test for stock-flow identification. In that case, model formulation becomes simpler for educators to teach and for students to learn. This idea is in the same philosophical line as enforcing good modeling practices in system dynamics software. For example, Powersim (Powersim, 2017), Vensim (Ventana, 2021), Stella (ISEE, 2023), and other major software do not allow for the equation of a stock being edited. For another example, Stella’s users do not have the option to edit the unit of flows. These units are automatically determined by dividing the unit of corresponding stocks by the simulation time unit.

A lack of restrictive guidelines could cause model formulation problems. System dynamics educators often leave the identification process open by using conditional statements such as “it depends.” This ambiguity might increase flexibility and foster creativity but could also lead to arbitrary model formulation practices. In a system dynamics thesis (Neugebauer, 2011), GDP, GDP growth, inflation, inflation policy, growth policy, monetary policy, and business cycles are all modeled as stocks. In such a system, decision points (flows) are shifted to second or third derivatives. Such conceptualization violates macroeconomic theory. Moreover, it makes the model unstable and prone to anomalous behavior. Such a model may fail to pass extreme condition tests because the flows are too sensitive to parameter selections. Above all, it has potentially destructive real-world policy implications. Putting decision levers on second and third derivatives could lead to significant overshoots before decision errors are corrected.

4.3 Future development

Besides educational implications, loose definitions and identification methods make it difficult to develop automated programs or computer codes to control models’ quality or standardize the modeling processes. Over the

years, system dynamicists have developed tools and methods to automate and standardize quality control of modeling and model documentation; see, e.g., Rahmandad and Sterman (2012); MartinezMoyano (2012). Computer programs that perform recursive checks on models need precise instructions for evaluating a specific criterion. To enable these programs, we need to refine our definitions and stock-flow identification tests to be clear, precise, and objective.

More restrictive identification guidelines also enable future possibilities for the use of AI in modeling processes. Given a clear problem statement, a computer program can formulate a model for it if stock-flow identification instructions are precise enough.

5 Identification Criteria

This section suggests tools and methods that enhance the clarity and robustness of stock-flow identification. First, we will have a concise but effective and practical definition of stocks. Second, the snapshot test will be tweaked for increased robustness and ease of use. Third, an additional test will be introduced to strengthen the snapshot test. Finally, a preliminary algorithm for systematic stock-flow identification will be presented.

It is worth reemphasizing that this paper is concerned exclusively with the conceptualization and not formulation of stocks and flows in a model (step 1 in Figure 1). That is, we try to determine the nature of a variable; whether it is stock or flow. If a variable is stock by nature, the modeler can model it as a stock, auxiliary, or constant depending on the time horizon of the model Richardson (2022). If a variable is flow by nature, the modeler can model it as a flow, if its corresponding stock is included in the model, or as an auxiliary, otherwise.

5.1 Redefining Stock Variables

Richardson and Pugh III (1981, 176) provide a solid definition for stock variables, helping us to take an important step toward the clarity and robustness of stock-flow identification. In their view, *stock* can be defined as “an accumulation over time, a storage device for material, energy, or information.”

While very concise, this definition is useful to identify a stock because it is consistent with the snapshot test and provides clear examples covering almost all types of stocks in any domain. Nevertheless, we might be able to

improve this definition using another definition of stock (Bossel, 2007c, p. 7):

State variables make up the “memory” of the system. Typically they are “stocks” of energy, resources, money, or individuals that change over time. The new level is determined from the level at the previous point in time where the state was last determined from the level at the previous point in time where the state was last determined, and from the inflows and outflows during the time interval. The state variables therefore reflect the sum of all state changes over a long period of time; they contain the “history” of the system.

The important aspect of Bossel’s definition is the notion of *memory* and *history* as key properties of stocks, as well as providing more categorical examples such as *resources*, *money*, and *individuals*.

With these considerations, let us redefine stocks as follows:

A stock variable is an accumulation over time, a storage for material, energy, information, resources, money, or individuals that preserves and represents parts of the system’s history.

5.2 Redefining the Snapshot Test

The next step toward clarity and robustness is to settle on a robust stock-flow identification test. The snapshot test, introduced earlier, is the most common tool for the testing. The refined definition of stock variables can be used to identify a stock preliminarily, but then we need to examine the accuracy of our identification.

We already saw Forrester’s description of the snapshot test; here is another one by Richardson and Pugh III (1981, pp. 176-7):

Imagine stopping time in the system, freezing all flows instantaneously, as if one took an all encompassing photograph of the system capturing intangible and invisible characteristics as well as physical processes. The potential level variables are those that still exist and have meaning in the snapshot. One would still be able to measure the extent of accumulations even if time were stopped, while flows would be stilled, perhaps visible in the photograph but not measurable.

This description is more useful than Forrester’s as it provides additional instructions for stock-flow identification. It introduces the notation of *meaning* and emphasizes *measurement* as factors to be considered for the identification test.

Nevertheless, the snapshot test provided above lacks clarity and is not helpful if the variables of interest are intangible. For instance, consider the concept of *utility*, defined as satisfaction or dissatisfaction gained from an action such as playing or listening to music (Langarudi and Bar-On, 2018). “If time were stopped,” would we “still be able to measure the extent of” satisfaction a person gains from playing music? This question is difficult to answer. On the one hand, if time stops, the music stops, and the utility flow stops. On the other hand, we can measure affection by the size of the pupil (Partala and Surakka, 2003). Therefore, one may suggest that we can measure the utility from a picture of the person’s eyes. Again, by definition, we know that utility is a flow concept (Samuelson, 1937). The change in pupil size is, in fact, a manifestation of the utility flow into the person’s brain. It is similar to pouring ink on a piece of paper. The visible stain of the ink on the paper (stock) is a manifestation of *pouring ink* (flow). It should be noted that different types of utility exist, and each could be flow or stock. The example mentioned above is an *instantaneous utility*, which is a flow concept. In contrast, “remembered utility” is an average utility, a piece of information stored in the brain, thus a stock concept. See Kahneman et al. (1997) for a comprehensive discussion.

Another example where the snapshot test fails to capture a variable’s type fully is the case of velocity. According to the test, velocity should still be measurable and meaningful if time stops. One could argue that both of these conditions hold if time stops. We can calculate the velocity at any point in time using the kinetic energy formula ($KE = \frac{mv^2}{2}$, where m is mass, and v is velocity). Also, at a standstill, velocity could be meaningful if we investigate the dynamics of velocity in relation to acceleration. Although both of these points might be valid, they cannot prove that velocity is a stock. The first point, i.e., being able to calculate a variable from other stocks of the system at any point in time, is, in fact, an indication that the concerning variable is a flow (Forrester, 1971, sec. 4.3). The second point, i.e., whether velocity is meaningful at a standstill, is a philosophical question and hard to yield any clear-cut conclusion.

To build a more robust test that will not fail under the conditions mentioned above, a slightly modified approach building on the snapshot test of Richardson and Pugh III (1981) is proposed. This approach suggests an additional question to be answered by modelers when deciding on a variable

type: “to measure the variable of interest, do we need to measure any other variable?” If a variable cannot be measured directly and requires measured values of other variables, it should be a flow. Such a variable cannot be a stock because it is, by definition, a derivative. Later in this paper, this approach is combined with another test for further strength and robustness.

5.3 Checking the Unit of Measurement

Another stock-flow identification test, which is mentioned in some textbooks, involves the use of units. Sterman (2000, p. 198) writes:

The units of measure can help you distinguish stocks from flows. Stocks are usually a quantity such as widgets of inventory, people employed, or Yen in an account. The associated flows must be measured in the same units per time period.

The text does not provide information on how the units can determine whether a variable is a stock or flow. A novice modeler may conclude that all variables with a time unit in their unit’s denominator should be flows. This conclusion is wrong, though. Consider “gallons per day” (or gallons/day) as an example. This unit has a time unit, “day,” in its denominator. Does it mean that its corresponding variable is a flow? It could, if the variable was, e.g., “water demand.” It could not, if the variable was an average, e.g., “perceived water demand.” It is the reason why some authors, as we saw earlier, have discouraged the use of units as an indicator of the variable type.

A more useful instruction is to deploy the units of measure to identify *stocks*. The question would be whether the variable’s unit of measure includes any time unit in its denominator. If the answer is *yes*, we cannot arrive at any conclusion. However, if the answer is *no*, the variable is definitely a stock. Note that variables with time-independent units, such as gallons, miles, pounds, heads, bits, etc., cannot be assigned to a flow. Therefore, a variable with such a unit is certainly not a flow, thus a stock. The opposite is not necessarily true. A stock variable may or may not have a time-independent unit.

5.4 A Preliminary Stock-Flow Identification Algorithm

Combining the updated snapshot and measurement unit tests, we can develop an algorithm to examine stock-flow identification. This algorithm (Figure 6) includes four questions that need to be answered by the modeler in a specific order to distinguish stocks from flows.

Figure 6: An algorithm to distinguish stocks from flows

The four questions are labeled as Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4. We also introduce a COUNTER, which counts the number of answers that may lead to identifying a STOCK. At the start of the process, COUNTER resets to zero.

Q1 asks if the variable of interest is an accumulation of material, energy, information, resources, money, or individuals. The variable will likely be a flow if the answer is *no*. If the answer is *yes*, COUNTER increases to two, and we proceed to the next question (Q2).

Q2 asks whether or not the variable's unit of measure includes any time unit in its denominator. If the answer is *no*, the variable is probably a stock, so we increase COUNTER by two. If the answer is *yes*, we proceed to the next question (Q3) and add only one to COUNTER. The reason for adding one to COUNTER is that the variable might still be a stock even if there is a time unit in the denominator of the variable's unit.

Q3 asks whether or not we need measurements of the variable at two or more points in time to arrive at its current value. The variable will likely be a flow if the answer is *yes*. If the answer is *no*, it is probably a stock, so we add two more to COUNTER. We proceed to the last question (Q4), then.

Q4 asks whether or not we need access to the measured value of other variables to arrive at the current value of the variable. The variable could be a flow if the answer is *yes*. If not, the variable is probably a stock, and we add two more to COUNTER.

Now that all the questions are answered, we count the number of times the variable was identified as stock. The variable is a flow if the number is 0 or 1 (COUNTER < 2). The variable is a stock if the number is equal or greater than 7 (COUNTER > 6). The identity is ambiguous at this stage if the number is bigger than 1 or smaller than 7 ($1 < \text{COUNTER} < 7$). In that case, more investigation into the nature of the variable will be required, meaning that our knowledge of the true nature of the variable needs to be revised to arrive at a correct specification. A stopgap might be to model the variable as an auxiliary until the variable is clearly identified.

Note that the presented algorithm does not help identify auxiliaries or constants (step 2 in Figure 1). For instance, consider *population density* as a variable. This variable represents the population of a species in a unit of land (e.g., hectare). Our algorithm will identify this variable as stock since it is a population type. Computationally, however, it might be easier (or more appropriate for your modeling purpose) to model the density as a division of the population stock by the stock of land. Therefore, in model formulation (step 2), this variable could be represented by an auxiliary rather than a stock.

6 Stock-Flow or Level-Rate?

To fundamentally fix the stock-flow identification problem, we should search for root causes of the problem. The knowledge of the system being modeled (or lack thereof) is probably the most critical factor in distinguishing stocks from flows. However, the terminology we use might also have an impact. In particular, the term “flow” might confuse people, who do not see anything flowing from velocity to position. In contrast, “rate of change of position” might be a better description of velocity.

Over time, we have changed our language about stocks and flows. Forrester originally used the terms level (for stock) and rate (for flow). Other classic textbooks (e.g., Richardson and Pugh III (1981)) also use the terms level and rate. By mid 1980s, the terms level and rate were already abandoned. In the inaugural article of *System Dynamics Review*, Richardson (1985) mentions stocks and flows but not levels and rates. Modern textbooks (e.g., Sterman (2000)) established the stock-flow terminology as the standard of the field.

The true causes of the terminology shift is not clear for the author of this paper. It might be a choice of simplification. The word flow seems to fit system dynamics diagrams better – the pipes with valves on them look like flows. The shift might have occurred due to the need for consistency with other disciplines such as economics, accounting, and management where the terms stock and flow are commonly used. Another reason might be the confusion the term “rate” could create with phenomena that are considered constants in other disciplines, e.g., fertility rate, interest rate, etc.

Despite the interdisciplinary inconsistency it may cause, the level-rate language seems to be more useful, more consistent with system dynamics theory, and easier to relate to the integration process than the stock-flow language, making it a better tool for stock-flow identification.

7 Conclusion

The lack of standardized and clear guidelines for model conceptualization and formulation could be detrimental to the field of system dynamics. The lack of clarity leads to a chaotic, arbitrary, and loose modeling style that allows almost any sort of modeling to be considered acceptable and *not wrong*, which is against the call for rigor and high-quality modeling (Homer, 2013; Sterman, 2018). Regardless of which school of thought we follow, empirical, structural, pragmatic, or methodological (Clancy et al., 2023), we

must continuously improve the education, standardization, and quality control of our modeling methods. Absolute freedom in model conceptualization and formulation might increase flexibility and creativity but also makes our method almost random leading to models that are messy and difficult to verify, validate, and reproduce.

This paper responds to the model conceptualization problems by developing an improved method for stock-flow identification. Stock-flow identification is defined here as distinguishing stocks from flows, which precedes the decision for whether a stock should be formulated as stock, auxiliary, or constant, or whether a flow should be formulated as flow or auxiliary. The goal is to close the gap by providing a clear and robust guideline to distinguish stocks from flows. Such improvement in the model formulation instructions contributes to the education of system dynamics, automated model evaluation and documentation, and standardization of modeling processes.

To achieve this goal, some of the major definitions of stock and flow and their limitations have been reviewed and discussed. In particular, we discussed how lack of clarity has led to an identity crisis for some flow variables. Then, current definitions and stock-flow identification tests have been modified to arrive at a new procedural identification method with potentially greater performance.

The stock-flow identification method developed here has some advantages over previous instructions. First, it synthesizes all useful guidelines, which are scattered in many different documents, in one single procedure (Figure 6). Second, it provides a more accurate and robust identification method through subtle adjustments to the current methods. Third, it provides a basis for further improvement in our stock-flow identification methods.

This, or any similar method in general, does not provide an ultimate solution for the stock-flow identification problem. Such methods may not yield *correct* answers if our understanding or definitions of the concept at hand are poor or deficient. Stocks and flows could be understood differently depending on modelers' worldview (Mass, 1980).

To complement our systematic identification method and reduce inconsistencies even further, we can develop a publicly open and online repository listing all variables and their type. The repository could initially be populated with variables well-known to all, e.g., population, price, inventory, reservoir, etc., and then expand over time. Additions to the repository could occur through a voting system requiring the approval of a selection committee. This repository can ultimately eliminate the need for the iden-

tification procedure (Figure 6). Such an effort could contribute to system dynamics education, quality control, and standardization of our modeling approach.

Finally, we might need to reconsider and revise the terminology we use. As discussed in this paper, the terms “stock” and “flow” (as opposed to the older terms, “level” and “rate”) might have contributed to the ambiguity of our conceptualization methods. Future research could investigate the evolution and impact of the terminology on the performance of the system dynamics method.

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